

MICROMECHANICAL ANALYSIS OF 3-D COMPOSITES

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3-d composites, especially those made by Sol-Gel-Synthes method are becoming now more and more popular in various applicatons. Temperature fields of different nature and external stress fields produce microstructural stresses, which can exceed adhesive or cohesive strengths of the matrix and the reinforced particles. But micromechanical analysis is needed also in obtaining the average, or 'homogenized' properties of a composite, such as elasticity tensor, linear thermal expansion tensor etc., obtained by two-scale asymptotic analysis.

To solve typical 3-d cell problem of a composite, numerical analysis is needed. For numerical implementation such methods as finite difference (FDM), finite element method (FEM), fast Fourier transform method (FFTM), boundary element method (BEM) can be applied. The great advantage of the latter is the reduction of a 3-d problem to a 2-d one. While those BEM variants which lead to the second kind Fredholm equations are, in general, not applicable to the cell-problem because of cell corners and edges, the BEM formulations connected with the first kind Fredholm equations and separate surfaces supporting vector densities, are better adjusted for the solution of the cell-problem.

The indirect BEM formulation which leads to the first kind integral equations is presented bellow. Let Ω_0 denote the translating-invariant typical cell, containing N reinforced particles, occupying regions Ω_i , $i=1, \dots, N$, such that $\bar{\Omega}_i \cap \bar{\Omega}_j = \emptyset$, $i \neq j$, so none of the particles contact with each other, but instead separated by the matrix material. With minor modifications of the present method it is possible to regard the case of non empty intersections $\Omega_i \cap \Omega_j$ and the case 'particle-inside-particle', which represents thick coated particles. Corresponding boundaries of the cell and particles will be denoted $\partial\Omega_0, \partial\Omega_1, \dots, \partial\Omega_n$.

In the boundaries $\partial\Omega_i$, $i=1, \dots, N$ between particles and matrix an ideal mechanical contact is assumed, so

$$(1) \quad u_{(i)}|_{\partial\Omega_i} = u_{(0)}|_{\partial\Omega_i} ; \quad t_{(i)}|_{\partial\Omega_i} = t_{(0)}|_{\partial\Omega_i} ; \quad i=1, \dots, N$$

where $t_{(i)}$ -corresponding tractions, $u_{(i)}$ is the displacement field. For the cell boundary translate-invariant conditions should be given

$$(2) \quad u_{(0)}(x') = u_{(0)}(x) - A \cdot (x - x')$$

$$\frac{\partial u_{(0)}(x')}{\partial e_p} = \frac{\partial u_{(0)}(x)}{\partial e_p} ; \quad x' \in \Gamma'_p, \quad x \in \Gamma_p$$

where $e_p, p=1,2,3$ -basis in R^3 of the translation group of a periodic structure;
 $\Gamma'_p, \Gamma_p \subset \partial \Omega_0$ -opposite sides of the cell-boundary, so the cell itself is homeomor-
 phic to a cube; A -external deformation tensor.

To construct a periodic solution of (1), (2) auxiliary surfaces are chosen in such way,
 that $\bar{\Omega}_0 \subset \Omega_0$, while $\Omega_i \supset \bar{\Omega}_i, i=1, \dots, N$ so the surfaces $\partial \Omega_i, i=0, \dots, N$ have no inter-
 sections with boundaries $\partial \Omega_j, j=0, \dots, N$. Now integral representation for the dis-
 placement in matrix material has the form

$$(3) \quad u_{(0)}(x) = \sum_{i=0}^N \int_{\partial \Omega_i} E_{(0)}(x-y) \cdot d\mu_{(i)}^0(y), \quad x \in \Omega_0 \setminus \left(\bigcup_{i=1}^N \Omega_i \right)$$

where $E_{(0)}$ is Kelvin's fundamental solution; $d\mu_{(i)}^0$ -unknown vector Radon's measure
 on $\partial \Omega_i$. It should be noted, that $u_{(0)}$ satisfies equations of equilibrium everywhere
 in Ω_0 . Similar procedure can be used to derive integral representations for reinfor-
 ced particles

$$(4) \quad u_{(i)}(x) = \int_{\partial \Omega_i} E_{(i)}(x-y) \cdot d\mu^i(y), \quad x \in \Omega_i$$

where auxiliary surfaces $\partial \Omega_i$ satisfies condition $\bar{\Omega}_i \subset \Omega_i$.

Substitution of the representations (3),(4) into (1),(2) gives a system of the linear
 integral equations, which in operator form can be written

$$(5) \quad B(d\mu) = g$$

where $d\mu = \Pi d\mu^i \times \Pi d\mu_i^0$ while right-hand side g is equivalent to the right-hand side
 of (1), (2).

The solution of (5) can be obtained with the regularization techniques. With minor
 modifications of this method, it is possible to construct the solutions of the thermal
 microstructural stresses in 3-d composites.